

Views, Attitudes and Needs Assessment Questionnaire

December 2022

RRIZSCALE

RESPONSIBLE RESEARCH & INNOVATION ECOSYSTEMS AT REGIONAL SCALE

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PROJECT INFORMATION

TITLE	RRI2SCALE – Responsible Research and Innovation Ecosystems at Regional Scale for Intelligent Cities, Transport and Energy
START DATE	1 January 2020
DURATION	36 months
WEBSITE	https://rri2scale.eu/
COORDINATOR	AGENZIA PER LA PROMOZIONE DELLA RICERCA EUROPEA - Italy
PROJECT OVERVIEW	RRI2SCALE has designed a robust methodological approach to assist regional R&I governance systems to effectively and sustainably address their Regional Dilemmas. Techno-moral scenarios will be “tested” via JRC’s Scenario Exploration System and Regional Dialogues, forming the basis for elaborating Regional Agendas and Roadmaps towards the integration of RRI principles into territorial R&I design. All project results will form the RRI2SCALE Toolkit for replication by other territories.
CONSORTIUM	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. AGENZIA PER LA PROMOZIONE DELLA RICERCA EUROPEA https://www.apre.it/ 2. HOGSKULEN PA VESTLANDET https://www.hvl.no/ 3. UNIVERSITEIT MAASTRICHT https://www.maastrichtuniversity.nl/ 4. UNIVERSITEIT TWENTE https://www.utwente.nl/en/ 5. Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL ADVISORS PC https://qplan-intl.gr/ 6. RESEARCH AND INNOVATION MANAGEMENT GMBH https://www.research-and-innovation-management.com/ 7. WHITE RESEARCH SPRL https://white-research.eu/ 8. HORDALAND FYLKESKOMMUNE https://www.hordaland.no/ 9. PROVINCIE OVERIJSEL https://www.overijssel.nl/ 10. KRITI https://www.crete.gov.gr/ 11. AXENCIA GALEGA DE INNOVACION http://gain.xunta.gal/

The present document provides a questionnaire that local or regional authorities can use to understand their citizens' views, attitudes and needs in preparation for the upcoming policy design phase.

Welcome note

Dear participant, **welcome** to our survey!

The survey lasts **about 5 minutes**. There are no right or wrong answers. It is all about your views. All data is anonymised, and your privacy is guaranteed. Thank you very much in advance for your support, which is very much appreciated! If you have any questions, please do not hesitate to contact us via **[insert the mail address of data collectors]**

Best wishes,

The **[name of regional project or initiative]** team

[A one-paragraph brief description about the regional project or initiative can be added before the survey]

SECTION 0 — ELECTRONIC CONSENT

Before proceeding, we would like to kindly draw your attention to the following information:

PARTICIPATION

Your participation in this survey is voluntary. You may refuse to take part. Please be aware that if you do decide to participate, you may also stop participating at any time without penalty. There are 10 questions in this survey related to Responsible Research and Innovation, including processes or concerns in your region.

BENEFITS

You will receive no direct benefits from participating. However, your responses may help us to improve our work.

RISKS

There are no foreseeable risks involved in participating in this survey. By answering the questionnaire, you grant permission for the data generated from this questionnaire to be used **ONLY** for research purposes. The results will be disseminated in scientific publications and public reports wherein anonymity will be guaranteed. Regarding the dissemination plans, you can find more details via the following link **[insert relevant link or website]**. Participants' utterances will be used in reports as quotes, but in such a way that anonymity is ensured. To sum up, any information provided remains ANONYMOUS!

CONFIDENTIALITY

Your survey answers and data will be stored in a password-protected electronic format. We do not collect any identifying information, such as your name, email address, or IP address. Therefore, your responses will remain anonymous. No one will be able to identify you or your answers, and no one will know whether you participated in the study.

CONTACT

If you have questions at any time about the study or the procedures, you may contact via email at **[insert relevant mail address]**

ELECTRONIC CONSENT

Please select your choice below.

Clicking on the "Agree" button indicates that:

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ You have read the above information. ✓ You are clearly informed. ✓ You voluntarily agree to participate. ✓ Your anonymous answers can be used for research purposes. ✓ You are 18 years of age or older. 	<input type="checkbox"/> Agree
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Before starting, we would like to give you a simple definition of *innovation* that we use for this survey. More specifically, we refer to *innovation* as a set of new technologies and forms of organisation that reshape regional activities. It may include new digital services in various areas (e.g., transport or smart cities), as well as community activities that result in more effective collaborative actions (e.g., recycling or energy production).

SECTION 1 – IDENTIFICATION OF PRIORITY AREAS AND FUTURE TRAJECTORIES

In this section, we would like to get your views regarding the most important areas for investing in your region. This will help us provide regional authorities with a comprehensive list of priorities based on your preferences. The second question aims at identifying insights about your perceptions regarding the future trajectories of your region.

1. In the following list, please indicate which areas you would choose your region to spend money on.

	Low Priority	Medium Priority	High Priority
Provide grants for research and innovation activities			
Provide support to small and medium-sized businesses to develop and apply new technologies			
Support citizens and companies to use renewable energy sources by subsidising them			
Create new digital public services that are more easily accessed			
Upgrade transport facilities making them smarter and more efficient (rail, road, or airports)			
Skills development through vocational training activities			
Create new public spaces and infrastructures that serve regional specific social or environmental needs			
Other (Please specify: _____)			

2. In the long run, I believe that my region should be mainly shaped as (max two options):

- a hub of innovative small and medium-sized businesses that will attract highly skilled workers
- a highly-digitalised public sector region that uses citizen-friendly applications
- an energy-efficient region characterised by optimised energy production processes using renewable energy sources
- a high-mobility region that uses smart transport for optimising access, distances and time
- a high-quality-of-life region where citizens are heard and participate in addressing their daily life needs

SECTION 2 - POTENTIAL TRADE-OFFS BETWEEN INNOVATION AND RISING SOCIETAL CHALLENGES

In this section, we ask your opinion about potential conflicting aspects between innovation and rising societal challenges, such as negative environmental effects or exclusion of specific social groups from policy design processes.

3. Please indicate your agreement with the following arguments:

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
I believe that promoting innovation should be a higher priority than citizens' well-being (such as jobs, income, housing, health, and safety).					
I believe that innovation should be boosted even though it might create gender inequalities in my region.					
I believe that it is good to support innovation when it has a positive impact on smart cities, energy, and transport, even if it requires access to my personal data.					
I believe that innovation outcomes for facilitating smart cities, energy and transport should be boosted, even if I might not have all the necessary skills to use them.					

SECTION 3 - TRUST TO LOCAL INSTITUTIONS AND PUBLIC PARTICIPATION

In this section, we want to explore general and institutional trust-related innovation, as well as your willingness to participate in regional innovation policy design processes.

4. In terms of general trust, I trust organizations or groups of people when they:

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
assess the effects of innovation in an independent way					
look at the effects of innovation from different angles					

clearly indicate which interests they have in innovation					
communicate in an open way about innovation					

5. Please indicate to what extent you trust the following organisations in your region.

	Not at all	Not much	Indifferent	A little	Very much
Regional government					
Local government					
Civil society organisations					
Non-Governmental Organisations					
Researchers/scientists working for universities					
Small and medium businesses					
Large companies					
Gender balanced governing bodies					

6. Please indicate your agreement with the following arguments:

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
I believe that citizens should be actively involved in helping to design regional innovation policies					
I believe that citizens should be actively involved in helping to evaluate regional innovation policies					

7. Which of the following ways would you choose if you wanted to get involved in public dialogues? (max 2)

- individual direct communication (e.g., individual meetings, letters etc.)
- online channels (e.g., platforms, social media accounts etc.)
- formal working groups (online and live) representing a community or group
- open events organized by public authorities (e.g., workshops)
- Other (Please specify: _____)

8. Have you ever been involved in public dialogues?

- Yes
- No

9. To what extend are you willing to be involved in future public dialogues related to:

	Not at all	Yearly	Monthly	Weekly	Daily
smart cities					
transport					
energy					

SECTION 4 – BACKGROUND INFORMATION

10. Gender:

- Female
- Male
- Binary
- Prefer not to mention

11. Age group:

- 18 – 24 years old
- 25 – 34 years old
- 35 – 65 years old
- More than 65 years old

12. Please indicate your educational level:

- No or Primary education
- Secondary education
- Higher education (Bachelor’s degree or equivalent)
- Higher education (Master’s, PhD or equivalent)

13. Please indicate your activity status:

- Employed
- Unemployed
- Retired
- Student
- Household activities
- Other

14. You participate in this survey as part of:

- Academia or research
- Government
- Business
- Civil Society – General public

15. Do you have any additional comments you would like to include? (optional)

(Free text)

16. I want to be informed about the survey results (optional)

- Yes
- No

Contact email (please insert the email where you wish to receive our future updates): _____

- I do consent to receive newsletters and updates from [name of project, initiative, organisation].

Survey end

Thank you for taking part into this survey and contributing to our understanding of what people think about Responsible Research and Innovation! Your input will help us a great deal to identify key elements and perceptions that should be considered during the implementation of our project. Do you have any questions or comments? You can contact us at [insert relevant mail address]

Informed consent

[The survey should include an informed consent section so that the process is GDPR-compliant. Below is the informed consent that was used in the RRI2SCALE project survey, and it may serve as an example for future surveys]

This privacy policy details information collection practices related to your personal data and other related information and the limited manner in which the RRI2SCALE project will use and disclose the information provided to us when you responded to the survey.

By participating in the survey, you voluntarily consent to the collection and use of your information by RRI2SCALE as set forth in this privacy policy. If you have any questions concerning this privacy policy or our data collection practices, you may contact us at info@white-research.eu. We reserve the right to change this privacy policy at any time and inform all participants about the updates.

In addition to your opinion, we are collecting some personal information such as age, country of residence and educational status for socio-demographic purposes. The collected data will be saved and used until the end of the research period of the RRI2SCALE project. The data will be only used for the purpose of the RRI2SCALE, funded under the European Union Horizon 2020 program, aiming to promote Responsible Research and Innovation principles for Regional Innovation Policies across Europe.

The lawfulness of the processing of personal data is determined pursuant to Article 6 of the EU's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). With respect to personal data, the processing of personal data is based on consent.